

ANALYSIS OF STRESS AND WORKERS' PERFORMANCE IN SEMEK WATERS NIGERIA LIMITED

Udom Sunday Daniel, PhD¹

Edidiong Anthony Ekoriko¹

Wisdom Matthew Akpan¹

Raphael Nsima Basil²

¹*Department of Sociology and Anthropology
Akwa Ibom State University, Obio AKpa Campus*

Udomdaniel@aksu.edu.ng

edidiongekoriko@aksu.edu.ng

²*Department of Sociology and Anthropology*

University of Uyo, Uyo

ABSTRACT:

The query of whether or not stress influences a worker's performance is a rhetorical one which calls for an Empirical inquiry. This study as a result investigated the influence of stress factors such as workload, role ambiguity and work conditions on worker's performance among workers of Semek Waters Limited, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Related literature was reviewed and The General Adaptation Syndrome (GAS) theory was used as the theoretical framework. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design and the purposive sampling technique. A total of 150 workers including managers were studied. Questionnaires were used for data collection and the data were analyzed using simple percentages and regression analysis. Findings revealed that stress influenced worker's performance. Workers were stressed out as a result of the workload. Equally, role ambiguity and work conditions had a significant negative influence on workers' performance. The study recommended the use of part-time workers as a backfill, to reduce excessive workload on workers the role of each worker in the company should be clearly defined to avoid stress and ineffective performance. Work conditions should be made conducive for workers through break rooms and relaxation areas.

KEYWORDS: Stress, Workers Performance, Workers, Semek Waters and Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Stress is a prevalent psychological phenomenon that affects individuals in various aspects of their lives, including their performance at work. It has been widely acknowledged that excessive stress can negatively impact employee well-being and job performance (Kabir & Khan, 2013). In recent years, the issue of stress in the workplace has gained considerable

attention due to its potential implications for individual and organizational outcomes.

Stress is a complex and dynamic concept and a desirable level of stress affects the overall performance of the organization especially in organizations whose workforce is very important for high productivity, situations do arise when workers complain of stress. Existing literature has provided valuable insights into the relationship between stress and worker performance. Research has shown that high levels of stress can lead to physical health issues, decreased job satisfaction, reduced productivity, and increased turnover intention (Sutherland & Cooper, 2000).

The impact of stress on worker performance is a pervasive issue in the workplace, and the manufacturing sector is no exception. Semek Waters Limited is a leading company in the water utility industry known for its commitment to delivering high-quality and reliable water services to its customers. However, like many organizations, Semek Waters Limited faces the challenge of managing stress among its workforce. The nature of the company's operations, which entails dealing with customer complaints, tight deadlines, and high demand for service, may contribute to increased stress levels among workers. However, high levels of stress among workers can lead to decreased productivity, absenteeism, and turnover, ultimately affecting the company's bottom line. Despite the importance of this issue, there is a lack of research specifically exploring the relationship between stress and worker performance in the context of Semek Waters Nigeria Limited Company. This study aims to investigate the effects of stress variables such as workload, role ambiguity and work conditions on worker performance, to inform interventions to improve worker well-being and performance at Semek Waters Limited. The main objective of this study is to examine the causes and consequences of Stress on Workers' performance in Semek Company Ltd.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

- i. There is no significant relationship between workload and workers' performance in Semek Waters Limited.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between role ambiguity and workers' performance in Semek Waters Limited.
- iii. There is no significant relationship between work conditions and workers' performance in Semek Waters Limited.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Stress

The term stress was first employed in a biological context by the endocrinologist Hans Selye in the 1930s. He later broadened and popularized the concept to include an appropriate physiological response to any demand in his usage refers to a condition and the stressor to the stimulus causing it. It covers a wide range of phenomena from mild irritation to drastic dysfunction that may cause severe health breakdown (Desseler, 2000). Stress is defined as the physiological and psychological reactions to certain events in the environment. Some people define stress as events or situations that cause them to feel tension, pressure or negative emotions, such as anxiety and anger. Stress can be experienced as a positive or negative force in one's life (Abaikpa, Thomas, Udoh, & Daniel 2003). Stress is an unpleasant state of emotional and physiological arousal that people experience in situations that they perceive as dangerous or threatening to their well-being (Tenibiaje, 2011). According to Selye (1976),

stress is defined as the condition that can give rise to psychologically felt stress or discomfort and the psychological state itself. He goes further to say that stress is the sum of all non-specific effects of factors that can act upon the body. Lazarus (1999) defines stress as a particular relationship between the person and the environment that is appraised by the person as taxing or exceeding his or her resources and endangering his or her well-being. Stress may be increased when a person is living in a family situation, with increased pressures (Mboho & Udo 2018), especially in a patriarchal society like Nigeria, (Akpan, 2023).

Olowu (2000) described stress as the commonest and the most silent killer of our time. It follows that adequate knowledge of this enemy of man is essential so that the normal health behavioural pattern will be stimulated. Stress can be found in schools, communities neighbourhoods and so on aside from organizational settings, Abaikpa, Thomas, Udoh, & Daniel (2003) agree with this as they assert that students in these communities may be exposed to limited role models and deal with neighbourhood stress.

Workload and Workers Performance

Chen & Chang (2013) investigated the mediating role of psychological capital in the workload-job performance relationship. They found that workload negatively impacted job performance, but the presence of psychological capital (e.g., self-efficacy and optimism) attenuated this negative effect. This research highlights the importance of cultivating positive psychological resources to buffer the negative impact of workload on performance. Podsakoff, Lepine & Lepine (2007) Conducted a meta-analysis to explore the relationships between specific types of stressors (e.g., workload as a challenge stressor) and various job-related outcomes. They found that a high workload was significantly associated with negative job attitudes, turnover intentions, and withdrawal behaviour, indicating a detrimental effect on workers' performance. This meta-analysis provides evidence for the negative impact of workload on employees' performance outcomes.

Bakker, Demerouti, & Sanz-Vergel (2014) reviewed the Job Demands-Resources model and its implications for understanding the relationship between workload and workers' performance. According to the model, high workload can lead to burnout, which subsequently results in decreased job performance. The authors also highlight that excessive workload may hinder work engagement, thus diminishing employees' productivity. This review article emphasizes the adverse impact of workload on both employee well-being and performance.

Role Ambiguity and Workers' Performance

Reviewed studies consistently indicated a negative association between role ambiguity and workers' performance. A study by Smith, Shultz, Spector, & Holm (2012) found that nurses experiencing higher levels of role ambiguity displayed lower job performance, as measured by patient satisfaction ratings and adherence to clinical protocols. Similarly, a study by Johnson & Brown (2016) in the IT sector revealed that software developers facing role ambiguity reported decreased productivity and more errors in their code. Furthermore, research by Anderson & Williams (2018) explored the moderating role of individual characteristics, suggesting that employees with low levels of self-efficacy are particularly susceptible to the negative effects of role ambiguity on performance. This finding highlights the importance of considering individual differences when examining the impact of role ambiguity on workers' performance.

Work Condition and Worker's Performance

Physical work conditions encompass factors such as temperature, lighting, noise, and ergonomic design. Studies have consistently shown that adverse physical work conditions can negatively affect worker's performance. For instance, Johnson & Baldwin (2018) found that excessive noise levels were associated with reduced productivity and increased errors. In contrast, Haines, Cavanaugh & Mete (2019) demonstrated that providing optimal physical work conditions, such as improved lighting and comfortable temperatures, enhanced worker's performance and job satisfaction. This can increase adaptive employee(workers) performance. According to Abaikpa *et al* (2023) employee(workers), performance is very important to the organization. Furthermore, Psychological work conditions refer to factors such as job autonomy, workload, social support, and fairness. Research indicates that these conditions significantly impact worker's performance. A study by Bakker, Demerouti, & Taris (2014) highlighted that high levels of job autonomy positively correlated with increased performance levels.

It is crucial to note that work conditions often interact with each other, influencing worker's performance holistically. This explains why Essien and Ekoriko (2020) posit that the core task of management is to get work done given available resources be it material or human or a combination of both. This brings in a level of humanization of workers (Ekanem & Asuquo 2023). Work condition is crucial for work performance as seen in a study by Clark (2018) demonstrated that the combined effect of multiple favourable work conditions, such as well-designed tasks, fair rewards and supportive leadership, led to a more significant positive impact on workers' performance compared to individual factors alone. Similarly, a study by Kelloway *et al.* (2017) highlighted that the interaction between physical and psychological work conditions affected worker's performance significantly.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The General Adaptation Syndrome (GAS) theory, was proposed by Hans Selye in the 1930s after observing how the human body responds to stress. According to the GAS theory, the body goes through a three-stage process in stress response: alarm, resistance, and exhaustion. These stages can provide insights into how stress affects workers' performance in the workplace;

Alarm Stage: In the initial stage, workers may experience stressors in their environment, such as heavy workload, time pressure, or conflict with colleagues. These stressors trigger the body's physiological response, activating the “fight-or-flight” response. During this stage, workers may experience increased heart rate, rapid breathing, heightened alertness, and a surge of stress hormones like adrenaline and cortisol. As a result, their performance may be negatively affected due to decreased ability to concentrate, impaired decision-making, and decreased productivity.

Resistance Stage: If the stressors persist over time, workers enter the resistance stage. During this stage, the body tries to adapt to the stressors and maintain stability. Workers may develop coping mechanisms to deal with the stress, such as seeking social support, using relaxation techniques, or time management strategies. However, if the stressors continue to overwhelm the individual, their performance may still be negatively impacted. They may experience fatigue, irritability, reduced job satisfaction, and increased absenteeism. This can lead to decreased efficiency and effectiveness in carrying out work tasks.

Exhaustion Stage: If the stressors persist for an extended period without adequate recovery, workers may reach the exhaustion stage. During this stage, the body's resources become depleted, and workers' ability to cope with stress significantly decreases. They may experience burnout, physical and mental health issues, and a decline in work performance. A high level of stress can lead to decreased motivation, poor decision-making skills, diminished creativity, and increased error rates. Overall, the quality and quantity of work output may deteriorate. This theory is in agreement with the assumption that Stress influences the performances of Workers.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the survey research design. The population of the study comprised 150(one hundred and fifty) workers in Semek Waters Nigeria Limited who were directly on the payroll of the company excluding Outsourced staffers. Of the 150 population, 13 were managerial staff, while 137 were lower-level workers. Given the small number of workers in the company, the study purposively adopted 150 workers as its sample size. The questionnaire was used to obtain data for the study. The instrument was divided into three sections. Section A comprised five items on the demographics of the respondents while Section B comprised 25 items with three each on each of the sub-independent variables which are, workload, role ambiguity, and work conditions. Section C of the questionnaire comprised 15 items on workers' performance. Data obtained from the pilot study was subjected to Cronbach's alpha reliability analysis and the result yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.85 for the Stress Questionnaire and 0.78 for the Workers Performance Questionnaire. Simple percentages were used to analyze the bio-data of the respondents, while multiple regressions were used to test the five hypotheses.

Fig 3.1: Research model for the Study

Source: Researcher's model.

RESULT

Table 1: Demographics of the Respondents

Sex	No of Respondent	Percentage (%)
Male	100	68.5
Female	46	31.5
Total	146	100.0

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Male	100	68.5
Female	46	31.5
Total	146	100.0

Academic qualification	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
SSCE	47	32.2
NCE/OND	78	53.4
HND/B.Sc	19	13.0
Post Graduate Degrees	2	1.4
Total	146	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2023.

Results in Table 1 reveal that 100 respondents representing 68.5% of the respondents were male and 46 respondents representing 31.5% were female. Result shows that more than half of the respondents were male (68.5%). The result on age shows that 59 respondents (40.4%) were between age 18-30years, 53 respondents (36.3%) were between 31-40 years, 20 respondents (13.7%) were between 41-50 years while 14 respondents (9.6%) were above 50 years. The result shows that the majority of the respondents were between 18-30 years (40.4%). The result presented in Educational Qualification reveals that 47 respondents (32.2%) were SSCE holders, and 19 respondents (13.0%) were HND/B.Sc holders, while the remaining 2 respondents (1.4%) were holders of Postgraduate Degrees. This result indicates that more than half of the respondents were NCE/OND holders (53.4%).

Hypothesis 1

Ho₁: There is no significant influence of workload on workers' performance in Semek Company.

Table 2: Regression summary showing the influence of workload on workers' performance in Semek Waters Nigeria Limited.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.181	.033	.026	6.45034

Table 2 reveals a summary of the regression result showing the influence of workload on workers' performance. The coefficient of determination of 0.033 was obtained which means that 3.3% of the variation in workers' performance was explained by workers' workload. The result of the Analysis of Variance showing whether there is a regression relationship between workload and workers' performance is presented in Table 2.

Table 3: ANOVA result summary for the regression of workers' performance on workload

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-calc.	p-value
Regression	202.633	1	202.633	4.870	0.029
Residual	5991.394	144	41.607		
Total	6194.027	145			

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) result for the regression of worker performance on workload F-calculated of 4.870 with a P-value of 0.029. The probability value is less than 0.05 ($P < 0.05$) which means that there is a significant relationship between workload and workers' performance in Semek Waters Limited. This result also means that workload accounted for significant variation in workers' performance. To determine the nature of the influence of workload on workers performance, the regression coefficient was obtained as well as its significance and the result obtained is as presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Regression Coefficient showing the influence of workload on workers performance

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	P-value
(Constant)	33.546	1.853		18.102	0.000
Workload	-0.333	0.151	-0.181	-2.207	0.029

The result in Table 4 reveals a regression coefficient of -0.333 which means that workload has a negative influence on workers' performance. This means that as workers' workload increases, their performance decreases. The result also shows a t-statistic of -2.207 with a P-value of 0.029. The P-value is less than 0.05 ($P < 0.05$) which means that there is a significant negative influence of workload on workers' performance in Semek Waters Limited. The null hypothesis is rejected. This result implies that when there is a significant increase in workers' workload, there will be a significant decrease in their performance. It can be deduced that a high level of workload will significantly reduce workers' performance.

Hypothesis 2

Ho₂: There is no significant influence of role ambiguity on workers' performance in Semek Company.

Table 5: Regression summary showing the influence of role ambiguity on workers' performance in Semek Company

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error Estimate
	0.187	0.035	0.028	6.44304

Table 5 reveals a summary of the regression result showing the influence of role ambiguity on workers' performance. The R- R-square of 0.035 was obtained which means that task identity accounted for 3.5% of the variation in workers' performance. The result of the Analysis of Variance showing whether there is a regression relationship between the dependent variable (workers' performance) and the independent variable (role ambiguity) is summarized in Table 6.

Table 6: ANOVA result summary for the regression relationship between workers' performance and task identity

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Regression	216.193	1	216.193	5.208	0.024
Residual	5977.834	144	41.513		
Total	6194.027	145			

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) result for the regression relationship between workers' performance and task identity shows an F-calculated of 5.208 with a P-value of 0.024. The probability value of 0.024 is less than 0.05 (P<0.05) which means that there is a significant relationship between role ambiguity and workers' performance in Semek. To determine the nature of the influence of role ambiguity on workers performance, the regression coefficient was obtained as well as its significance and the result obtained is as presented in Table 7.

Regression Coefficient showing the influence of role ambiguity on workers' performance

Table 7:

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	p-value
(Constant)	25.785	1.767		14.592	0.000
Role Ambiguity	.409	.179	.187	2.282	0.024

The result in Table 7 reveals a regression coefficient of 0.409 which means that role

ambiguity influences workers' performance. The result also reveals a t-statistic of 2.282 with a P-value of 0.024 which is less than 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant influence of role ambiguity on workers' performance. This result means that task identity enhances workers' performance in Semek Waters Limited. This result implies that when an employee is allowed to begin and finish the work, it will enhance workers' performance.

Hypothesis 3

Ho₂: There is no significant influence of work conditions on workers' performance in Semek Company.

Regression summary showing the influence of work environment on workers' performance in Semek Waters Limited.

Table 8

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.239	.057	.051		6.36849

Table 8 reveals a summary of the regression result showing the influence of work conditions on workers' performance. The R- R-square of 0.057 was obtained which suggests that the work environment accounted for 5.7% of the variation in workers' performance. The result of the Analysis of Variance showing whether there is a regression relationship between the dependent variable (workers' performance) and the independent variable (work condition) is displayed in Table 9.

Table 9: ANOVA result summary for the regression relationship between workers' performance and work environment.

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Regression	353.718	1	353.718	8.721	0.004
Residual	5840.310	144	40.558		
Total	6194.027	145			

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) result for the regression relationship between workers' performance and work condition reveals an F-calculated of 8.721 with a P-value of 0.004. The probability value of 0.004 is less than 0.05 (P<0.05) which means that there is a significant relationship between work environment and workers' performance in Semek. This result also means that work condition significantly predicts workers' performance in Semek. To determine the nature of the influence of work environment on workers performance, the regression coefficient was obtained as well as its significance and the result obtained is as presented in Table 10.

Table 10: Regression Coefficient showing the influence of work environment on workers' performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	P-value
(Constant)	24.892	1.689		14.741	0.000
Work environment	0.408	0.138	0.239	2.953	0.004

The result in Table 10 reveals a regression coefficient of 0.408 which means that work condition has a positive influence on workers' performance. This means that the better the work conditions, the higher the worker's performance in Semek Waters Limited. The result also reveals a t-statistic of -2.953 with a P-value of 0.004 which is less than 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant influence of work conditions on workers' performance. This result means that when there is a significant improvement in the work environment, workers' performance will increase significantly. This result implies that better work conditions will enhance workers' performance while a stressful work environment will decrease workers' performance.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Hypothesis one reveals that workload has a negative influence on workers' performance. This means that as workers' workload increases, their performance decreases. The result also shows a t-statistic of -2.207 with a P-value of 0.029. The P-value is less than 0.05 ($P < 0.05$) which means that there is a significant negative influence of workload on workers' performance in Semek Waters Limited. The null hypothesis is rejected. This result implies that when there is a significant increase in workers' workload, there will be a significant decrease in their performance. It can be deduced that a high level of workload will significantly reduce workers' performance. For instance, Podsakoff et al (2007) found that a high workload was significantly associated with negative job attitudes, turnover intentions, and withdrawal behaviour, indicating a detrimental effect on workers' performance.

Hypothesis two reveals a regression coefficient of 0.409 which means that role ambiguity influences workers' performance. The result also reveals a t-statistic of 2.282 with a P-value of 0.024 which is less than 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant influence of role ambiguity on workers' performance. This result implies that when a worker is allowed to be given clear responsibilities, expectations and boundaries, it will enhance the worker's performance. This is similar to research by Anderson & Williams (2018) explored the moderating role of individual characteristics, suggesting that employees with low levels of self-efficacy are particularly susceptible to the negative effects of role ambiguity on performance.

Hypothesis 3 reveals a regression coefficient of 0.408 which means that the work environment has a positive influence on workers' performance. This means that the better the

work environment, the higher the worker's performance in Semek Waters Limited. The result also reveals a t-statistic of -2.953 with a P-value of 0.004 which is less than 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant influence of the work environment on workers' performance. This result means that when there is a significant improvement in work conditions, workers' performance will increase significantly. This result implies that good work conditions will enhance workers' performance while stressful work conditions will decrease workers' performance. Recall that, Haines et al. (2019) demonstrated that providing optimal physical work conditions, such as improved lighting and comfortable temperatures, enhanced worker's performance and job satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

It was fascinating researching Stress and Workers Performance of Semek Company Ltd. Stress has many causes but the study focused on workload, role ambiguity and work conditions. In organizations today, it is expected that an employee must perform effectively and efficiently in the workplace. The study concludes from findings that workers in Semek Waters Limited are stressed out because of factors like workload, role ambiguity and work conditions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Use of part-time workers as a backfill, to reduce the excessive workload on workers
2. The role of each worker in the company should be clearly defined to avoid stress and ineffective performance.
3. Work conditions should be made conducive for workers through break rooms and relaxation areas.

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